

season and on about 30,600 ha in the 1976–77 wet season.

IR26 was first reported to be damaged by the BPH in September 1976. In February 1977 hopperburn was confirmed in IR26 and IR34, and IR30 was severely attacked (see photo). At three locations, IR32 appeared resistant; at one location, IR36 seemed resistant. The highest BPH populations (adults + nymphs/hill) were 1,008 on IR26, 1,508 on IR30, 47 on IR32, 18 on IR34, and 40 on IR36. Most of the insects were in the first and second instars, except for two cases of more advanced insect development on IR26. No hill in 11 fields was found infected with symptoms of grassy stunt; 24% infection was observed in 1 field. On December 15, 1976, the Extension Service of the N. Sumatra provincial government estimated the total area of rice fields attacked as 43,618 ha, with 3,482 ha of hopperburn. On 31 January 1977, 43,783 ha of BPH damage was reported, with 7,597 ha of hopperburn. About 9,400 ha of the damage and 880 ha of the hopperburn were on IR26. This was the first report of large areas of IR26 being severely attacked by the BPH in Indonesia. ❧

Population fluctuation of brown planthopper in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* is a major rice pest in Kerala. Its first reported outbreak was in the punja crop of 1973–74. It caused extensive damage in Kuttanadu, Alleppey district, and in the Kole areas of Trichur district.

These rice-growing tracts are waterlogged and the fields must be drained after the monsoon rains for paddy cultivation. Rice is extensively grown, mostly as a monoculture crop. After one or two rice crops, the fields remain under water for the rest of the year. Notable features of rice cultivation in these areas that may favor the BPH are widespread cultivation of susceptible high yielding varieties, such as Jaya and IR8; high

seeding rates; excessive nitrogen use; indiscriminate insecticide application, which causes destruction of natural enemies; and favorable climatic factors.

The Rice Research Station, Moncompu, concentrates its efforts on the BPH problem through a multidisciplinary approach. To study the population fluctuations, we have recorded light-trap catches of BPH in Kuttanadu since January 1974.

The population peaks twice each year, in each cropping season. The maximum catch was recorded from January to March, with the highest peak in February. Interestingly, this peak coincides with the booting and postflowering stages of the main crop (Oct.–Nov. to Feb.–Mar.). Hopperburn and serious crop losses are common during this period. The BPH population begins to decline by late March when the harvest ends and continues to drop until July. The next peak is from July to September, during the autumn crop. But because of adverse climatic conditions, such as heavy rains and high winds, the population does not rise to alarming proportions during this period, and so the crop is safe. The light-trap studies also show that BPH are present throughout the year. Survival of the pest during the off-season, when there is no standing crop, should be further investigated. ❧

Varietal resistance to the rice thrip, *Baliothrips biformis*

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Baliothrips biformis is primarily a pest of seedling paddy which emerges in the drier months and infests the late-planted crops in both crop seasons in Sri Lanka. Depending on the degree of infestation, the insect can retard growth or kill the seedling. Breeding for thrip resistance would be the most economical means of control. Of the almost 800 indigenous varieties that underwent preliminary observation, those that showed reasonably good levels of resistance were field-tested in replicated trials

during the 1976 and 1977 dry seasons. Damage was observed at 2 weeks after seeding or at the 3- to 4-leaf stage. The system of evaluation was as follows.

Reaction ¹	Damage
R	Leaves remained healthy except for very slight rolling of the first and second leaf.
MR	Slight rolling and withering of the first and second leaf.
MS	First and second leaf withered and dead; upper leaves slightly rolled.
S	Upper leaves rolled, withered, and with few white lesions; lower leaves dead.
HS	Upper leaves dying with pronounced white lesions, seedlings are stunted; lower leaves dead.

¹R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

Varieties found resistant and moderately resistant to the pest are listed below.

Variety	Reaction
Dahanala 2220	R
Dahanala 682	R
Kaluheenati 547	R/MR
Heenati 896	MR
Mudukiriyal 197	MR
Kalubalawee	MR
Demalakotan 1630	MR
Gonabaru	MR/MS

Serious attacks of rice gall midge in the central plain of Thailand

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has long been one of the most important rice pests in northern and northeastern Thailand, but not in the central rice-growing area. In June 1977, however,

gall midge severely attacked the second crop of rice about 80 km east of Bangkok, in Bangkhanarg village, Bangnampriew district, Chachengsao province. A survey was conducted in the village in June and July.

Rice is irrigated throughout the year. A second crop of about 480 ha of high yielding varieties (mostly RD) has been directly sown during March and April since 1976. The insecticides carbofuran

3G and monocrotophos 50% E.C. were applied at about 45 and 60 days after sowing, but they were not effective because the application was late. Precipitation was 5.5 mm in March, 54.7 mm in April, and 121.0 mm in May.

From 85 to 95% of the hills were infested. From 1 to 11 galls per hill were found; the average was 3. The hills averaged four panicles each.

The severe outbreak may have

occurred because 1) the village is adjacent to Prachinburi province where the insect was previously found at low levels; 2) the susceptible RD varieties are widely grown, supplying ample food; 3) rice is planted at high density by broadcasting; 4) irrigation throughout the year creates a suitable environment for gall midge reproduction; and 5) a high rate of fertilizer is applied.

Varietal reaction to rice @ midge, leaf rollers, and thrips

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In the Vaigai-Periyar river project of Tamil Nadu, the rice gall midge *Pachytiplosis oryzae* and the leaf roller *Chaphalocrosis medinalis* have become serious because of extensive and intensive cultivation of high yielding varieties.

The relative susceptibility or resistance of 85 prerelease cultures was assessed in a randomized field experiment with three replications at the Agricultural College and Research Institute Farm, Madurai, in 1975–76. Because a severe outbreak of the rice thrip *Baliothrips biformis* was noticed in the nursery stage, the varieties were also observed for their reactions to

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge, leaf rollers, and thrips at Madurai, India.

Cultivar	Gall midge (% affected tillers)	Leaf roller (% affected leaves)	Thrips (n0./5 sweeps)
Most resistant varieties			
W. 1263	1.0	6.4	10.5
Kakatiya	6.8	1.8	5.0
CR 57-49-5	7.5	3.2	3.0
Isawarakora	1.5	3.4	7.0
PTB 10	7.4	3.7	3.5
PTB 21	7.8	4.6	2.5
Leang 152	8.0	6.2	2.5
CR 58-51	8.1	6.9	6.0
CR 95-R-14-1	8.2	7.8	9.5
CR 57-29 (non-pigmented)	8.8	8.1	3.5
CR 57-29 (pigmented)	9.6	9.6	—
Most susceptible varieties			
GMR 5	50.6	—	—
Cul. 4609	—	29.1	—
Co 36	—	—	66.5

the insect. Eleven varieties had fewer infestations by the three pests than did the others (see table). The variety

W. 1263 showed resistance to gall midge; Kakatiya, to leaf rollers; and PTB 21 and hang 152, to thrips.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

The influence of varying depths and durations of submergence on the adaptability of rice varieties to low-lying waterlogged conditions in West Bengal, India

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Three hundred rice varieties were tested in eight specially constructed fields under shallow water, knee-deep water, semideep water, and deep water conditions at the Chinsurah station during the 1974–75 monsoon season. The experiments were conducted in randomized blocks with

two replications; each plot was 7 × 3 m. The soil was clay loam with a pH of 6.9. No manure was applied. The figure shows the extent of adaptability of promising low-lying varieties to varying waterlogged situations together with method of sowing, growth duration, and grain yield.

The findings suggest that Achra 108/1, CNL 214, and CNL 231 have a maximum degree of ecological adaptability to varying waterlogged conditions and can be grown in shallow water, knee-deep water, and semideep water. Similarly, Patnai 23, Tilakkachari, Kumargore,

CNL 270, and NC 1281 are well adapted to shallow and knee-deep water. Pankaj, CNL 312, NC 678, OC 1393, IR442-2-58, Kalma, and Raghusail grew well only in shallow water. CNL 180, CNL 31, Chakia 59, and Jalamagna have moderate adaptability and were found suitable for knee-deep and semideep water. Varieties such as CNDW 13, CNDW 395, Jaladhi 1 and Jaladhi 2 show great ecological adaptability to the greatest depth and duration of submergence; they can grow in both semideep and deep water. Typical floating rice varieties such as